

PROCEDURAL VIDEO-AIDED INSTRUCTION IN TEACHING AND LEARNING COOKERY

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ABSTRACT

The landscape of education is continually evolving, shaped by the dynamic demands of a rapidly changing global economy and the need for students to acquire relevant skills for their future careers. This experimental study investigates the effectiveness of procedural video-aided instruction in improving the academic performance of Grade 10 students in Cookery. The research aimed to address the gap in traditional instructional methods by incorporating innovative video resources tailored to enhance learning outcomes. Conducted at Sta. Maria Integrated High School, the study involved grade 10 students as respondents. Through a carefully designed experimental setup, students were exposed to instructional videos specifically crafted to guide them through various cookery procedures. These videos were meticulously developed to provide comprehensive step-by-step instructions, visual demonstrations, and explanatory narration to facilitate effective learning. The research methodology employed quantitative measures to assess the impact of procedural video-aided instruction on student academic performance. The findings of the study revealed a significant improvement in the academic performance of students who utilized the developed instructional videos compared to those who relied solely on traditional teaching methods. The incorporation of procedural videos positively influenced students' understanding, retention, and application of cookery concepts and techniques. This research contributes valuable insights into the potential of procedural video-aided instruction as a supplementary tool in teaching and learning cookery for grade 10 students. By harnessing the power of multimedia resources, educators can create dynamic learning environments that cater to diverse learning styles and enhance student engagement. The study underscores the importance of integrating innovative instructional approaches to optimize learning outcomes and prepare students for success in practical domains such as cookery.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Assessment, Cookery, Delivery, Instructional Support, Modular Distance Learning, Procedural Video-Aided Instruction*

INTRODUCTION

The landscape of education is continually evolving, shaped by the dynamic demands of a rapidly changing global economy and the need for students to acquire relevant skills for their future careers. Bonfield et al., (2020) stated in their study that as we evolve into the world of digital age, so is the teaching approaches and techniques. For years, the Philippine educational landscape has been changing in order to better and elevate its current standing and to meet the educational needs of every Filipino. The Department of Education implemented the K to 12 Curriculum, which covers Kindergarten and 12 years of basic education, including six years in primary school, four years in junior high school, and an additional two years in senior high school, replacing the 2002 Basic Education Curriculum. Cookery in Technology and livelihood Education focus primarily in the practice of preparing food for consumption for Grade 10 learners. On the other hand, Technology and Livelihood Education subject play a vital role in developing students' technical skills and transforming their lives (Segundo 2022). It can be recalled that through the enactment into law of Republic Act No. 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, or simply the K to 12 Law, Department of Education retained cookery subject in the junior high school curriculum Technology and Livelihood Education.

Educational system is being strengthened by the Republic Act No. 10533 or also known as Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 as stipulated under Section 10.3, which states:

“The production and development of locally produced teaching and learning materials shall be encouraged. The approval of these materials shall be delivered to the regional and division education unit in accordance with national policies and standards”. This act implies that the creation of learning resources that play an important part in the conduct of teaching-learning processes is encouraged. Given the current condition of the controlled and experimental group, is the procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery effective?

As the educational sector faces challenges brought by the pandemic, utilization of procedural video-aided instruction in cookery would ameliorate the students' knowledge and skills acquisition particularly in preparing vegetable and seafood dishes. In addition, the procedural video-aided instruction material in cookery will provide more concrete learning on students than just reading modules given the current education situation brought by the pandemic. Hence, high academic performance of the student will be achieved.

Research Questions

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pre-test score of the control and experimental groups in cookery?
2. What is the post-test score of the control and experimental groups in cookery?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test scores of control and experimental groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the post-test scores of control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of control and experimental groups?
6. Is the procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery effective?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in the Second Quarter of the calendar year wherein the selected topic for the study falls in the second quarter about cookery specifically vegetable and seafood dishes and it was based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).

The post-test was given to assess the students' performance and how much they learned from the materials used. This was administered in the same manner as the pretest. The results were recorded and compared to the pretest results to see if students improved their academic performance.

The following statistical treatments were applied to the collected data: 1) Scores were used to determine the pretest and post-test results and to establish the outcome of the evaluation, and the validity of the generated video-based learning materials; and 2) paired t-test was used to determine the significant differences between the pretest and post-test scores of the control and the experimental groups. This study was carried out to determine the efficacy of procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery.

RESULTS

With regards to the effectiveness of the procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery, it shows the effectiveness of the procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery. The post-test means of Experimental and Control Group are 40.52 and 36.11 with standard deviation of 4.94 and 7.83, respectively. The cohens d is 0.6721 and probability value of <0.001 which is less than the threshold probability value of 0.05; therefore, the researcher's decision was to reject the null hypothesis.

Group	Post-Test Mean	SD	Cohens d	p-value	Interpretation
Experimental	40.52	4.94	0.6721	<0.001	Moderate Effect
Control	36.11	7.83			

Thus, these imply that there is a moderate effect of the procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery. This also implies that the use of procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery is beneficial to students' learning. Supporting this is the study conducted by Mayer, Fiorella, & Stull (2020), where, instructional videos largely contributed to students' learning in the field of Educational Technology.

DISCUSSION

Video lessons have also been shown to be highly effective as a tool for improving teaching quality.

The procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery is effective as the result showed Moderate Effect, implying that students maximized their learning experiences and excelled their knowledge with the use of procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery.

In addition, there are researchers who designed a mobile app for teaching vocabulary to students where they found out that clear and easy to understand learning instructions are the key to students' independent learning.

More about this, it also emphasized in that learning materials should contain clear and concise instructions for it to be easy to follow and understand, thus ensuring independent learning from students.

Conclusions

The procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery is effective; therefore, students learn best using independent learning through the use of academic videos which also poses characteristic of personalized learning.

The School shall develop strategies and materials that will help improve academic performance, particularly for laboratory subjects that require performance tasks as means of validating the ratings of learners. They shall produce instructional materials and can share this as best practice with the district. In this manner, no learner will be left behind.

Recommendations

Out of the conclusions drawn, the researcher recommends the following:

1. It is recommended for subject teachers to encourage students to navigate online academic videos about cookery to gain more knowledge on the subject.
2. The use of procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery is highly recommended for teachers to adapt and use in teaching the cookery subject.
3. Further utilization of online academic videos in line with cookery is highly recommended.
4. Since the procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery is effective, development of video material for other topics and subjects is highly recommended in the next studies.
5. Learning materials and modules are useful in the teaching and learning process, therefore, their use along with the videos is highly recommended.
6. The actual use of procedural video-aided instruction in teaching and learning cookery across all sections of Grade 10 taking cookery is highly recommended.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher obtained permission to conduct this study from the principal's office at Sta. Maria Integrated High School. Following the principal's approval, the instrument was distributed to collect all of the necessary data to achieve the study's goal. The researcher personally supervised the distribution of questionnaires to respondents to ensure that any questions or clarifications were provided.

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